

THE METHODOLOGY OF CONDUCTING A LINGUACULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE PECULIARITIES OF EXPRESSING THE EMOTIONS OF HEROES IN KAZAKH AND ENGLISH LEGENDS IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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Abstract

The relevance of considering the expression of the emotional component in legends is due to the need for in-depth study of the language, culture and thinking of peoples through folklore texts, building links between emotions, cultural codes and linguistic resources. The purpose of this study was to develop a methodology for the linguacultural analysis of the expression of emotions of characters using the example of Kazakh and English legends in literature lessons. The following methods were used in this study: linguacultural, contextual analysis, comparative, analytical and synthetic, experimental method. In the course of studying the linguistic and cultural features of the expression of emotions in legends, a methodology of linguacultural analysis was created, consisting of four stages: consideration of the emotional range, assessment of the specifics of the linguacultural background, study of the relationship between linguistic cultures and the expression of emotions, consideration of linguistic resources used for this purpose.

Thus, in Kazakh folk legends, linguistic cultures, mythopoeic means, historical plots, landscape descriptions were used, and in English legends – linguistic cultures, historical plots, a variety of implicit means. The experiment conducted on the basis of the Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University and the Bolashak University of Kyzylorda, before and after the application of the developed methodology of linguacultural analysis, the participants of which were students of 1-2 courses, showed the following results: on average, the indicator of awareness in cultural, folklore and literary processes increased by 6-8%, although in some parameters the indicators reached 12-13%. In the future, the results of this study can be used to compare large folklore genres for the emotional component, consider linguacultural phenomena, and develop techniques to study the specifics of expressing emotions in literary texts.

Keywords: folklore, mental state, concept, folk customs, historical context.

Introduction

The study of linguacultural analysis techniques is necessary from the point of view of understanding the importance of national cultures in the modern world. With the help of newly developed strategies of linguacultural analysis, it is possible to come to important conclusions regarding the cultural, spiritual and social development of entire peoples. Thus, linguacultural approaches are relevant not only within the framework of literature, but cover a whole range of interdisciplinary knowledge.

Consideration of folklore texts through the prism of the trinity of language, thinking and culture allows us to understand the specifics of expressing emotions based on the national mentality. Since literature models real life, using the example of characters' images, it is possible to analyze what range of emotions they experience, what linguistic resources are involved for this, what linguacultural codes are used to enhance the emotional component in the texts of folk historical legends. Comparing several linguistic cultures gives an understanding of how different the perception and transmission of emotions can be.

In pedagogical discourse, the study of the connections between the expression of emotions of a character and the peculiarities of the spiritual culture of a people can be used as a tool for educating students of patriotism, love for folklore and traditions in literature lessons. Therefore, the disclosure of the characters' images through the prism of national traits is necessary, first of all, to preserve the historical connection between generations.

Literary texts are inherently precedent-setting, since they have many interpretations. In the work of Zh.T.Balmagambetova (2020), such precedents were considered as part of the national picture of the world, correlated with stereotypical thinking and mass consciousness. Thus, the study examined the linguacultural space of Kazakhstan, but did not provide a comparative analysis with other linguistic cultures.

The linguistic means used for the folklore genre and insufficiently studied in linguaculturology were considered in the work of N.F.Bayramova (2022). Attention was focused on the methodology of linguacultural analysis, but the study is theoretical and does not contain practical conclusions.

A comparison of Scottish and Kazakh toponyms is presented in the work of A.Meirbekov (2023) based on the analysis of legends. A range of topics considered in the works was highlighted: heroism, memory, bravery, respect for ancestors, and attention was focused on the transformations of the characters. This paper presents a comparative analysis of two linguistic cultures, but the main focus is on toponymy, not on the expression of emotions.

The subject of study in the work of E.Rudan (2022) became an expression of emotions in the oral literary tradition. The research focuses on the consideration of emotions from a folklore point of view, taking into account the genre of folk tales, in particular the emotion of fear. In this paper, the linguistic mechanisms of conveying the emotional state of the characters have not been considered.

The purpose of this study was to develop a methodology for the linguacultural analysis of folklore texts using the example of legends written in Kazakh and English. To achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were set: 1) to study the features of expressing the emotional state of characters and ways of conveying emotions using linguistic resources (artistic tropes, stylistic figures), linguistic cultures (linguistic concepts) and linguacultural background; 2) to investigate the effectiveness of the developed methodology for linguacultural analysis in Kazakh universities. The subject of consideration was the folk historical Kazakh and English legends, in particular about Korkyt, Robin Hood and King Arthur.

Theoretical overview

The following problems become the subject of consideration in modern research: building associative links between emotions and linguacultural elements, forming an idea of literary patterns, studying basic and complex emotions, and new ways of transmitting them. The peculiarities of code switching, the use of folklore texts for teaching, and consideration of the links between psychological theories and literary criticism were also actively studied.

The presence and interaction between the conceptual categories of nostalgia and heroism is indicated by S.T.Allison (2020). It is impossible not to agree with the author that nostalgic experiences cause associative connections with the manifestation of heroism and form certain cultural patterns for imitation.

The study of the emotional sphere in literary studies is presented in the collection of essays by Ja.Ingeborg (2017). In this work, the relationship between the emotional components of the aesthetic and non-aesthetic plan is studied, and attention is paid to the emotional models that affect the perception process. French, English, German, and American literature were used as examples.

In the work of S.Ullah (2020) provides an overview of the basic expressions of emotions, which were divided into seven main groups: neutral, anger, fear, surprise, happiness and sadness. The merit of the author was the study of complex expressions of emotions that arise when combining several of the above.

The use of smiley varieties in order to convey key emotions that are easily recognized was considered in the work of A.Charbonnier (2021). The results of the study of "new" emoticons have shown that they play an important role in the process of transmitting emotions using communication technologies and social networks. Other ways of expression, such as facial expressions, are not as effective.

Thus, most modern research is based on the study of the links between folklore, psychology, literary studies and cultural studies. It should be noted that in modern research, the problem of conditioning emotions with the help of socio-cultural factors plays a significant role. Since literature is a projection of real life, the study of the emotions of characters is directly related to the consideration of their behavior, reactions, and mental states.

Materials and methods

The study of the features of the expression of the emotional component was carried out on the basis of folk legends of Kazakhstan and Great Britain, in particular, such texts were used: "Bashpai" (Kazakh legend) (Zharar, 2021) and "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow" (English Legend) (Stories to grow by, 2023). These folklore materials were examined for the use of linguistic cultures, various artistic techniques and a range of linguistic resources for expressing emotions.

The methodology of linguacultural analysis was created on the basis of building links between the thinking, language and culture of the Kazakh and English peoples, in particular, it took into account the mechanisms of expressing the emotional component by using linguistic resources and cultural codes. Based on this, four key stages of the methodology of linguacultural analysis were derived: the first is the definition of the emotional range, the second is the consideration of the linguacultural background, the third is the study of the functions of linguistic cultures in the expression of emotions; the fourth is the consideration of linguistic means, including artistic tropes, to indicate the mental states of characters.

The experimental method in this study was used to study the effectiveness of the methodology of linguacultural analysis, developed to determine the manifestations of emotionality in the folklore of Kazakhs and the British. The experiment was conducted on the basis of two universities: Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University, "Bolashak" University of Kyzylorda. The participants of the experiment were 1-2 year students studying in the specialty "Kazakh language and literature". To determine the level of knowledge before and after applying the methodology of linguacultural analysis, a survey was used in which students assessed their knowledge according to the following criteria: "knowledge of historical legends", "familiarity with folklore images", "knowledge of history", "understanding the specifics of using linguistic cultures to express emotions", "understanding the artistic means used to express the emotional component."

Contextual analysis in this study was used to provide examples that confirm the theses about the use of certain linguistic means to convey the emotional component in folklore. Based on the analysis of contexts, data were obtained on linguistic resources used to convey emotions in the texts of folk legends, as well as on linguistic cultures used to enhance the emotional effect. Thus, on the basis of contexts, connections were built between thinking, culture and language in Kazakh and English literary texts.

Comparative analysis in this work was used to study the similarities and differences between the expression of emotions in Kazakh and English folk legends. The results of the comparison were presented in the table, the following criteria were taken into account: "assessment of the emotional state of the character", "use of linguistic culture", "introduction of a mythopoeic component", "use of historical plots", "transmission of emotions through landscapes", "direct reference to the emotional range", "use of implicit means to express emotions".

The analytical and synthetic method in this study was used to study theoretical issues related to linguaculturology, emotionality in literature and its means of expression, establishing links between folklore, culture and psychology of characters, conceptualization of folk culture, and the evolution of literary characters. Using the analytical and synthetic method, the key aspects considered in the research of modern linguists, cultural scientists, and psychologists were outlined.

Results

The psychological emotionality of the characters in literary works includes such aspects as spiritual worldview, psychological state, and features of the inner world. Among the main ways to display the emotions of characters are such as a portrait, description of actions, language and emotions. The depiction of psychological experiences is often accompanied by the transformation of the hero, in particular with a change in his thoughts, principles, statements, and the recognition of his own mistakes. All this contributes to the development of the storyline and the deepening of artistic works. With the help of truthful reflection of emotions, the reader finds answers to his questions, reveals his inner world (Li, 2022).

The developed method of linguacultural analysis of literature has been included in several stages. First, the range of emotions in Kazakh and English legends, during which it was proposed to discuss the topic of consideration and further discussion with the teacher. For example, the following quotes were selected from the Kazakh legend "Bashpai": «*Байқаусызда болған осы жағдай өле-өлгенше Қорқыттың есінен кетпей, өзін күнәлі сезініп, нұшайман болады екен*» – «*Ажал шіркін қапыда тұзаққа түсірді. Бір өкінішім – осы*» – «*Сол жерде Қорқыт соңғы күшін жиып, қобызын қолына алып, қарындасын жұбатқандай болып, бірер қайырым күй шалған екен*» (Zharar, 2021).

During the analysis and discussion in the audience, it was determined that there is an emotional buildup in the text: a sense of calm and security – anticipation of death – feelings of guilt and regret – a sense of sin – a benevolent mood. In the Kazakh legend, the principle of framing is used, since the emotional plane of the image of Korkyt moves from a positive emotion to strong negative experiences and then back to a positive emotion.

In order to determine the emotional background of the English legend "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow", the following passages were selected in the literature lesson: «*From then on, he made it known throughout the land that anyone seen hunting in Sherwood Forest would be grabbed at once and thrown into prison*» – «*Robin Hood did not like that one bit*» – «*Can't you see this is a trap? When they see you, they will grab you*» – «*Robin Hood said nothing. In his heart, he wanted to go*» – «*«Get him, you fools!» shouted the Sheriff*» – «*It would be his job to catch Robin Hood once and for all!*» (Stories to grow by, 2023).

After analyzing and discussing all the stated quotes in the lesson, such emotional reactions as anger, discontent, moralizing, silent reaction, insults, shout-

ing, irritation were highlighted. As a rule, laconic negative emotional reactions prevailed, and the mental state of the characters was transmitted through dialogical speech.

At the second stage of linguacultural analysis in the literature lesson, after determining the emotional palette of legends, it is necessary to study the linguacultural background, in particular the national customs presented in the text. Students should pay attention to the preservation of Kazakh traditions and customs using the example of "Bashpai". For example, the cult of ancestors, which is based on the worship of the dead and the belief in their magical power: «*Мен өлсем де, менің атымды атап, ұрпағымның есіне салып жатар*».

Death, according to this legend, is associated with a transition to another state, more calm and carefree: if during Korkyt's life he was accompanied by a feeling of guilt and regret, then after death he finds his peace in the performance of the melody "Bashpai", charming people. It is also necessary to focus on the Kazakh burial traditions: the fulfillment of a dying wish («*Өміріме серік болған қасиетті қара қобызымды өзіммен бірге көміңдер*»), crying for the dead («*көз алдында дәрменсіз шырылдаған қарындасымен*») (Zharar, 2021).

The linguacultural background of the English legend "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow" is not as colorful as in the Kazakh legend "Bashpai", but it is possible to note such traditions as deer hunting in Sherwood Forest ("*This King let the poor come into Sherwood Forest to hunt the deer to feed their families*"), a competition with a bow and arrow ("*to find out who is the best in the land with a bow and arrow*"). It should be noted by students that the feelings and emotions of the main character Robin Hood are conveyed implicitly in the text of the legend, with rare exceptions: "*Robin Hood did not like that one bit*". In fact, the emotional component is transmitted not verbally, but through actions. For example, in the context of "*Then all at once, they would jump out and rob those rich men. Then he would give the money to the poor*" it's about saving the poor, fighting inequality, and the phrase "*Then the man in green pulled off his disguise and threw it on the ground*" speaks of demonstrative behavior, self-confidence and a desire to show his advantage (Stories to grow by, 2023).

Thus, the main characters of the Kazakh legend "Bashpai" and the British legend "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow" have a lot in common. In particular, the basis of the legend of Robin Hood is the legend of a valiant knight, a hero, a noble leader who, with the help of forest robbers, robbed the rich and gave property to the poor, fighting social injustice near Nottingham in Sherwood Forest. The legend "Bashpai" tells about the fate of Korkyt, who is an akyn poet, the creator of kobyz, a national leader in search of eternal life. Each of the characters is key in the folk epic, acting as a leader: Korkyt – ideological, Robin Hood – militant (Zharar, 2021; Stories to grow by, 2023). The visualization of the characters' images is shown in Figure 1 (Figure 1).

Korkyt

Robin Hood

Figure 1. Visualization of images of Korkyt and Robin Hood

Source: prepared on the basis of illustrations for legends (Zharar, 2021; Stories to grow by, 2023).

The third stage of linguacultural analysis in the literature lesson focused on the study of the use of linguistic cultures to express the emotional state of characters. For example, the legend "Bashpai" used "korymba" (an ancient Kazakh stringed bow instrument), which performs an important linguistic and cultural function. This tool helped Korkyt to be inconspicuous, protecting him from death and giving him peace of mind, the silence of the korymba led the main character to death: «Осы кезде қобыз үнінің тынған сәтін пайдаланып, дәм салған қоржынмен бірге ілесіп келген сақиналы зәрлі жылан өрмелеп келіп Қорқытты шағып алады» (Zharar, 2021).

It is necessary to draw the attention of students to the discussion of the image of a snake, which in the Kazakh tradition has several meanings: 1) secret knowledge, wisdom; 2) creative creation and 3) a symbol of eternal life, renewal. Thus, the personification of death in the image of a snake, personifying danger and unpredictability, was used in the text to emphasize wisdom and precede a prosperous life in the new world.

Among the linguistic cultures in the legend "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow", it is necessary to highlight the bow, a weapon that was widely used in England and helped to win the Hundred Years' War. The main part of the work is occupied by a detailed depiction of a medieval battle of archers: "Most of them missed. Some landed on the target, but none came close to the center", "It landed right through William's bull's eye arrow, cutting it in half!" (Stories to grow by, 2023). Deer hunting is another custom reflected in the legend of Robin Hood. This tradition is described in many German legends, according to which the deer was considered an animal capable of scaring away a snake, therefore it became a symbol of fortitude, nobility, and moral qualities.

The last fourth stage of the analysis of the emotional expression of characters in a literature lesson re-

lates directly to the study of language parameters. Students were offered cards with the names of various linguistic tools to convey a mental state. For example, the "metaphorical expressions" card can be easily demonstrated with the help of Sister Aktamak's address to Korkyt, in which she compares it with a high mountain and gold: «Аға, ағатай, асқар тауым, алтыным!». In addition, the affectionate form of the noun "agatai" is used. In the following context: «Бірде Қорқыт қарындасының алып келген дәмін татып отырғанда алай-дүлей дауыл соғып, толқын тұрып, бұлардың берекесін алады» parallelism is used, since the negative experiences of the main character are implicitly transmitted with the help of strong wind and the onset of a storm (Zharar, 2021).

The study of linguistic elements used to reflect the emotional state in the legend "Robin Hood and the Golden Arrow" is necessary to understand the peculiarities of the national mentality. In particular, when analyzing a text in a literature lesson, students are looking for different linguistic tools to reflect emotions and experiences: 1) rhetorical questions ("Can't you see that this is a trap?"); 2) motivational suggestions ("Robin Hood, don't go to the contest!", "Get him, you fools!"); 3) insulting and derogatory lexemes: «Get him, you fools!», «That wimp!» said the Sheriff»; 4) monological specifiers (particles, the designation of the phraseological type): «It would be his job to catch Robin Hood – once and for all!»; 5) statement in the Future Simple (Future Indefinite): «From then on, he made it known throughout the land that anyone seen hunting in Sherwood Forest would be grabbed at once and thrown into prison»; 6) estimated characteristics: «He fears me! He didn't have the guts to come»; 7) metaphorical constructions: «they roared». There are also concise author's descriptions of the inner state of the characters: «Robin Hood said nothing. In his heart, he wanted to go» (Stories to grow by, 2023).

Table 1.

Comparative characteristics of the expression of emotions in Kazakh and English legends

A means of expressing emotions	"Bashpai"	"Robin Hood"
Assessment of the emotional state by the character himself	+	+
The use of linguistic culture	+	+
The introduction of the mythopoeic component	+	-
The use of historical plots	+	+
Conveying emotions through landscape descriptions and parallelism	+	-
A direct indication of the emotional state	+	-
The use of implicit means to express an emotional state	+	+

Source: prepared according to the results of our own research.

Based on the analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn in relation to the expression of emotions in Kazakh and English historical legends. Kazakh legends have a folklore and mythopoeic basis, in English legends historical plots, heroes, concepts are in the foreground. In Kazakh legends, the national flavor is expressed much more vividly, in particular through the demonstration of rituals, traditions, the use of linguacultural concepts (for example, kobyz). English legends are devoid of vivid folklore components, they are more focused on conveying the spirit of the historical era. Kazakh legends have demonstrated a wider palette for expressing the emotional state of characters – from a direct assessment of behavior and mood to implicit markers (parallelism, metaphors, allegory). In English legends, an assessment of the emotional state by

the character himself is rarely used, at the same time, a wide range of linguistic and artistic means for expressing emotions is demonstrated.

The evaluation of the presented methodology for linguacultural analysis before and after its application during the experiment on the example of texts of Kazakh and English legends showed an increase in students' knowledge not only in the linguistic and cultural field, but also in general led to the strengthening of literary and historical knowledge. This is evidenced by the following survey results (Table 2). Thus, the approximate average value of the increase in students' knowledge is 7%, and in general the values range from 13% to 4% according to various parameters.

Table 2.

The results of the application of the methodology of linguacultural analysis of legends

Criteria	Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda university		"Bolashak" university	
	Before applying the technique	After applying the technique	Before applying the technique	After applying the technique
I know the historical legends of Kazakhstan	71%	83%	68%	76%
I know the historical legends of Great Britain	51%	64%	53%	66%
I am familiar with the folklore images of Kazakhstan	75%	79%	77%	81%
I am familiar with the folklore images of Great Britain	45%	47%	44%	49%
I know the history of Kazakhstan	71%	75%	69%	74%
I know the history of Great Britain	63%	70%	59%	67%
I understand the specifics of using linguistic cultures to express emotions in Kazakh literature	52%	59%	56%	62%
I understand the specifics of using linguistic cultures to express emotions in British literature	47%	54%	48%	53%
I understand the artistic means used in Kazakh literature	74%	82%	75%	83%
I understand the artistic means used in British literature	39%	47%	37%	44%

Source: prepared according to the results of our own research.

Thus, the results of this study showed that Kazakh and English historical legends differ significantly in the nature of the presentation of emotions (implicit or explicit) in works, the range of artistic means used, and the establishment of linguacultural ties. The developed methodology of linguacultural analysis demonstrated a high degree of improvement in students' knowledge of linguistic and historical parameters, in particular, knowledge increased by an average of 6-8%. It should be noted that by analyzing the emotional component, results were also achieved in terms of analyzing the artistic nature of the literary traditions of Kazakhstan and Great Britain.

Discussion

The relationship between the characters in the literary text indicates a high degree of emotion. In the work of E.Kim (2020) emotional manifestations were considered as one of the features of a literary text and processed using recurrent neural networks. From the

linguistic side, it is possible to describe an emotion through the character who experiences it, and the reason, that is, because of what this condition arose. The author proved that the genre of the text significantly influences the choice of artistic means for describing emotional states. Based on the analysis of Kazakh and English legends, it can be concluded that in the genre of historical legend, emotions are most often manifested through folklore images, linguistic cultures, and linguistic features characteristic of a certain historical period. Thus, emotionality is transmitted through the prism of mythopoeics, anthropomorphism, and folk customs.

A study by A.Acerbi (2013) showed that in 20th-century books written in English, the frequency of using emotional words was about 4%. It should be noted that in different historical periods, the number of words for positive and negative emotions varied, but at the same time, the most lexemes concerned the emotions of

fear and disgust. An interesting conclusion of A. Acerbi (2013) was that since the early 60s, American English has become more emotional than the British version. It should be agreed with the author that in recent years the number of mood words actively used in the twentieth century has significantly decreased, which may indicate significant changes in the expression of emotions in modern literary texts. The results of our own research record the means of expressing emotions characteristic of the Kazakh and English medieval linguoculture of the V – XV century. Due to constant genre modifications, updating of artistic resources, and the use of new terminology to describe psychological states, the expression of the emotional component has changed significantly over the past century.

In particular, in understanding the importance of the emotional component in folklore texts, only S.J. Bronner (2016) studies folklore as a complex phenomenon, and when considering the expression of emotions in Kazakh and English legends, attention is focused on a specific genre. Both works also draw attention to cultural codes (concepts, linguistic cultures), which can also be used to express emotions.

This work demonstrated the stability of cultural patterns and linguistic coding schemes due to the preservation of concepts and the so-called "common memory" (memory of generations). The results of the study of Kazakh and English legends, in particular the expression of emotions in them, showed that the linguistic patterns of each nation for the transmission of basic emotions are different. For example, in English there is a tradition of expressing negative emotions through rhetorical figures, exclamation points, emotional specifiers, at the same time, the Kazakh tradition has demonstrated the use of mythopoetics (anthropomorphism, parallelism, linguistic and cultural images-symbols). Thus, the "common memory" of Kazakhs and British is significantly different, which is a confirmation of F. Karsdorp's (2019) thought about the stability of historical memory.

Thus, after comparing the results of modern research with the results of our own research, we can draw several conclusions. The problems of cultural linguistics, cultural studies, folklore studies, and conceptualology occupy a key place in literary studies, since the need to establish links between cultural, folklore, and historical codes is only increasing. The emotional manifestations of the characters are interesting from the point of view of literary evolution, in particular emotions as a product of mental activity are conceptualized in popular culture. The processing and comparison of texts takes place using modern technologies and using large data bodies for the most objective assessment. Folklore texts are of interest for the pedagogical field of research, in particular for the creation of effective methods of work in the classroom and outside the classroom.

Conclusions

The developed methodology of linguacultural analysis for use in literature lessons was divided into several stages: 1) the study of the emotional range, that is, naming the emotions that the characters experience;

2) assessment of the linguacultural background (traditions, customs, household items); 3) consideration of linguistic cultures that are used to convey the emotional component; 4) study of linguistic resources for expressing mental and emotional states. Based on these criteria, a comparative characteristic was carried out between the features of the expression of emotions in Kazakh and English folklore texts.

In particular, Kazakh folk legends used such means to express emotions as the assessment of the emotional state by the character himself, the introduction of linguistic culture, mythopoetics, historical plots, landscape descriptions, as well as implicit means. In the English folklore tradition, the characteristic features were the following: assessment of the emotional state of a character, the use of linguistic cultures, historical plots, as well as a variety of implicit artistic means from rhetorical figures to emotional concretizers and motifs.

Priority tasks in the future may include the following: studying the transformation of characters in the process of folklore transformations, in particular emotionally, considering changes in the use of linguistic resources to express basic and complex emotions, comparative analysis of the heritage of different cultures and historical periods. It should be noted that in the future scientific perspective, it remains important to build links between the national language, culture and thinking.

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